

**FOOD, HEALTH AND ENVIRONMENT RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURES
TO TACKLE EMERGING PRIORITIES**

Deliverable 3.2 Cross-Thematic Landscape

TECHNICAL REFERENCES

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Executive summary

This report provides an in-depth analysis of the cross-thematic landscape of services available across European Research Infrastructures (RIs), specifically addressing the FHERITALE core focus: understanding the impact of artificial materials, including micro- and nanoplastics (MNPs), and biomaterials, on food, health, and the environment. It is based on the data from the First Catalogue of Available Services ([Milestone 3](#)), on the White Paper on Key Selected Priorities (Deliverable 4.1)^[1], on the initial draft of technologies and services (Milestone 6), on the comprehensive List of Technology Needs (Milestone 7), and on the Categorization of Services and Technologies (Deliverable 5.1)^[2]. This report systematically identifies the key missing services in the Catalogue of Available Services and pinpoints services where current capabilities are underdeveloped providing an analytical foundation for future strategic developments within the FHERITALE project, particularly in informing work packages focused on gap analysis and technology roadmapping.

1. Introduction and background

The FHERITALE project is a concerted effort addressing significant strategic research challenges in the domain of artificial materials. One of its aims is to establish a roadmap to fill the gap in those services that are essential to European researchers for investigating the complex impact of artificial materials on human health and on the environment.

Early project activities, including a bibliometric study^[3] and expert consultations, culminated in the White Paper on Key Selected Priorities (Deliverable 4.1)^[1]. Deliverable 4.1 identified crucial research priorities, persistent challenges, and actionable recommendations for the field.

Milestone 3 initiated the systematic mapping of services available in European RIs, providing the first tangible inventory of capabilities. Milestone 6 provided a first draft of technologies currently used for research focusing on the key thematic priorities. This fed into Milestone 7, a list of technological needs and their technology readiness. Finally, these resulted in Deliverable 5.1 – the categorization of services and technology, which will set the framework for the cross thematic landscape of services provided here^[2].

The present report provides an update of the initial mapping and data collection reported in Milestone 3, integrating critical information from FHERITALE Work Package 5 about the current service landscape within European Research Infrastructures.

2. Methodology for Analyzing Available Services

The First Catalogue of Available Services was further analyzed, and updated with a classification according to the Service Readiness Classification (SRC) reported in Deliverable 5.1 and here repeated for clarity:

Category A: Fully Operational Services/Technologies

- Proven track record of use in real-world or user-relevant contexts;
- Validated protocols and workflows are already in place;
- Established access procedures (e.g. via user portals, service agreements);
- Available support infrastructure, including user training, documentation, or helpdesk;
- Compliance with quality, regulatory, or ethical standards (when and if relevant);
- Used routinely either in general labs or specialized Research Infrastructures (RIs) environments for the selected FHERITALE priorities.

Category B: Existing but Partially Aligned or Restricted Services/Technologies

- Service is operational but requires adaptation/customization to fit project needs;
- Limited access, e.g., only available via collaboration or at specific sites;
- Validation was done in controlled or non-standard environments;
- Lack of protocols adapted to the target sample, process, or application;
- Dependence on expertise not yet disseminated or documented.

Category C: Technologies Not Ready for Service

- No established workflows or SOPs;
- No external user access (internal prototypes or ongoing R&D only);
- Resources, technical limitations, or extreme specialization of the hardware prevent immediate implementation at RIs sites.

Furthermore, the catalogue is continuously updated by direct contact with the respondents of the targeted survey described in Milestone 3 who indicated that additional/novel services would likely be available within 2 years. For this deliverable, there was no update yet with regards to Milestone 3 in terms of services available.

Further refinement was achieved by integrating insights from Milestone 6, which provided an initial draft of technologies and services currently in use, and Milestone 7, which detailed specific technology needs related to micro- and nanoparticles research. This multi-faceted approach ensures a comprehensive evaluation of the current RIs service landscape.

3. Landscape of Available Services

The cross-thematic landscape of available services reveals an array of capabilities within European Research Infrastructures that are directly applicable to the FHERITALE project's scope.

While the majority of service types are well-represented across the ESFRIs participating in the survey, as also reflected in Figure 1 below, the analysis from Milestone 3 points out that certain techniques appear to be under-represented in the current catalogue of available services. While some services can have limited diffusion because of intrinsic high cost or specialization, this observation suggests potential areas for focused development or increased visibility within the RIs network.

Figure 1: FHERITALE cross-thematic landscape of services at the time of this deliverable.

Zooming in on the specific services, and applying the categorization from Deliverable 5.1, leads to the landscape of services shown in Figure 2, which highlights where specific services can be found and their corresponding SRC as defined in Deliverable 5.1.

Figure 2: Services have been grouped based on their presence across the various ESFRI infrastructures and according to their Service Readiness Classification (SRC), as defined in Deliverable 5.1. In general at the state-of-the art of RIs, some of these services (those classified as category C) lack maturity; however, those offered by the ESFRI Research Infrastructures included in the map tend to be significantly more advanced. This highlights the importance of involving these RIs in the roadmapping process.

4. Identification of Underdeveloped Services and Technological Needs

This section highlights opportunities to address current technological needs and enhance service areas within the RIs landscape that are poised for growth and development, in view of WP5/6 activities. A critical perspective, considering the data from M6 and Deliverable 5.1.,

and further using recent review works from the MNPs field focusing on MNPs characterization, highlight several areas requiring attention:

- **Advanced Analytical Methods for Nanoplastics:** Despite advancements in microplastic characterization, the technology for detecting and analyzing nanoplastics remains underdeveloped. This is due to the difficulty of sample preparation and separation for nanoscale particles, but also the limited resolution found in (spectro-)microscopic characterization techniques that have a high SRC for (larger) microplastics, such as FT-IR micro-spectroscopy (SRC = A, but specifically for nanoplastics would be B or C).^[4,5]

Specific needs include:

- **Detection of Smaller Particles and Improved Sensitivity:** The ability to accurately detect and quantify nanoplastics below 100 nm is a significant challenge; and the work and equipment needed to measure such particles is accompanied by higher costs and longer experiment times.
- **Advanced Spectroscopic and Imaging Techniques:** Requirements include enhanced Raman and FTIR spectroscopy (meaning going beyond their conventional diffraction limit), advanced NMR methods (Diffusion Spectroscopy and Relaxometry, Solid-State NMR for speciation) advanced electron microscopy (SEM, TEM with elemental analysis or e.g. EELS), and atomic force microscopy (AFM) combined with e.g. IR for high-resolution imaging and characterization.
- **High-Throughput and Untargeted Analytical Workflows:** There is a demand for methods that can efficiently process large numbers of samples and identify unknown plastic types or degradation products, which currently is hampered by sample preparation and diversity. Proper statistical analysis for e.g. epidemiological studies is limited by “low” sample throughputs, although e.g. mass-based analysis techniques show promising improvements in terms of sample output.^[6,7]
- **In-situ and Real-Time Monitoring:** The capacity for non-destructive, real-time analysis of micro- and nanoparticles in complex environmental and biological matrices is crucial but currently limited.

- **Standardization and Reference Materials:** A significant and persistent challenge across the field is the lack of standardized samples, methodologies, and quality control measures. The development and availability of certified reference materials, especially for nanoplastics in various biological and environmental matrices, is a critical need to ensure comparability and reproducibility of research findings. Milestone 7 specifically emphasizes the need for well-characterized polymeric reference particles and standard protocols for sample preparation and analysis.
- **Computational Modeling and Prediction:** Enhanced computational tools are needed to predict the environmental fate, behavior, and potential impacts of artificial materials. This includes modeling their transport, transformation, and interactions with biological systems from the molecular to the cellular and whole-organism levels, moving beyond purely experimental approaches.^[8]
- **Integrated Environmental-Human Health Assessment:** A more holistic approach is required to assess the interactions of micro- and nanoparticles across different matrices and ecosystems, and their combined effects on human health. This includes addressing the "environmental-human testing gap" for bioactive particles and additives, and the need for better instrumentation to regulate emerging contaminants. Milestone 7 highlights the need for advanced in vitro and in vivo models that mimic real-life exposure scenarios, and integrated omics approaches for comprehensive hazard assessment, which are all needed to come to a proper risk assessment which is still in its infancy at this time.^[9,10]

The identification of these critical needs is fundamental for guiding future FHERITALE activities. It provides a clear direction for fostering the development, optimization, and wider implementation of new or adapted services within the RIs network to address the most pressing challenges.

Within the targeted questionnaires, users were asked to also fill in services that they plan to offer within a 2-years timespan. For example, there have been explicit mentions of pyrolysis GC-MS, often advocated as one of the vital techniques to quantify plastics from (environmental) samples. At the timing of this deliverable, we are actively reaching out to these specific indications and will follow up on an updated map once more is established.

7. Conclusion

This Deliverable 3.2 report analyzes the current service landscape within European Research Infrastructures, supporting the FHERITALE project's main goal. Drawing on the survey, the First Catalogue of Available Services (Milestone 3), the White Paper on Key Selected Priorities (Deliverable 4.1), and other related milestones and deliverables, it gives an overview of existing capabilities and areas needing further investment.

Our analysis shows the existence of strong services for physical, chemical, and biological characterization of micro- and nanoparticles within ESFRI. However, it also critically highlights persistent technological needs in areas such as advanced nanoplastic detection and their chemical and structural characterization, the critical absence of widely adopted standardized methodologies and reference materials, the lack of validated experimental and computational approaches to investigate the interaction of nanoplastics with biological systems at various spatial and complexity scales. It also points to underused technologies and the need for integrated assessments of environmental and human health impacts.

This report supports later Work Packages by identifying service gaps for Work Package 6 and informing strategies for Work Package 7. By mapping the current state and opportunities for growth, it helps build a coordinated Research Infrastructure network to tackle challenges related to artificial materials in food, health, and the environment.

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